

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

AGATHOCLES

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Project abstract:

A.G.A.T.H.O.C.L.E.S. aims to explore the **training models** and the **collaboration networks** in one of the most dynamic industries of the ancient **Classical World**: the ceramic industry. For this purpose, the pottery industry is the most common reality in the ancient world to address issues of knowledge transfer, gender division and mobility. Nowadays, the study of the ancient **itinerant works** and the dynamics of craftsmen's **mobility** needs to move towards an '**Archaeology of Gesture**', which is a new approach related to the analysis of the **hidden ancient gestures** and **technological procedures**.

Numerous technological aspects related to the ancient artisanal '**hands**' and tools, usually invisible to the naked eye, can now become visible thanks to advances in **archaeometry**, **computational-imaging** technology and other innovative toolkit this project intends to adopt through an highly-**interdisciplinary** approach (also with the involvement of **forensic** and **experimental** archaeology).

Moreover, an unusual approach for the ancient Greek world is involved: the **Social Network Analysis**. SNA can in fact innovate the methodologies used to identify the workshops and can provide new procedures to define the **possible groups**, relationships, dependencies and elements that can explain the existence of this complex productive **network**.

Moving across **microscopic** analyses to **macroscopic** data-processing (related to the ancient dynamics of 'transmission-flow' of artisanal knowledge and skills), the project specifically addresses the case-study of the red-figure workshops in **Southern Italy** and **Sicily** (5th-4th century BC). These workshops, with their **extensive networks of itinerant specialists**, are ideal to investigate **training and collaboration** by focusing on five key aspects: a) collaborative patterns within the workshop, b) collaborative patterns with other

workshops, c) age and gender differentiation of workforce, d) workers' mobility, e) capacity of cultural adaptation of the ancient artisanal industries.

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AGATHOCLES - INITIAL DMP

1. DATA SUMMARY

The project is focused on the artisanal gestures related to painters' activities and the ancient Greek red-figure vases workshop organization.

The project will therefore collect some evidence to support the working hypothesis:

1. images of archeological red-figure vases to perform RTI and photogrammetry
2. digital microscope images of red-figure vases details to study technological features
3. ceramic samples for archaeometrics analysis
4. information on published red figures vases from relevant catalogues to develop SNA
- Social Network Analysis
5. video recordings of experimental archeological sessions on various aspects related to technological issues

No pre-existing material will be reused; information will be gathered through publications analysis (any source will be properly accounted for).

Data category	Data type	Format (ongoing)	Format preservation	Expected size
Textual	Report	.doc	.pdf/A	At this stage we can't estimate the expected size [around 200 Mb]
	Consent template			
Tabular	Spreadsheet	.xls	.csv	At this stage we can't estimate the expected size [around 300 Mb]
Visual	Images	.jpeg	.jpeg	At this stage we can't estimate the expected size [around 200 Gb - images will be stroed in 4 records nor exceeding 50G each]
	Images	.ptm	.ptm [format can not be converted as images would lost their interactive nature]	At this stage we can't estimate the expected size [around 200 Gb - images will be stroed in 4 records nor exceeding 50 Gb each]
	Video	.mp4	.mp4	At this stage we can't estimate the expected size [around 10 Gb]

2. FAIR DATA

To facilitate the usage and re-use of the stored data, all stored data will be accompanied by a text-based description of the data. The precise detail of the data format should be contained with a folder containing the data and named using a convention that readily identifies the source.

Measurement datasets originating from electronic instruments usually will themselves contain technical metadata describing the state of the instrument during data acquisition (i.e. Nikon photographic and recording video sets; digital microscope sets).

File naming:

alpha-numeric characters (a-z; 0-9) with location, shape and inventory number + underscore (_) + type of file (photo; video; microscope; etc.)

ex. Lipari-Calyxkrater-11190_microscope.jpeg

Folders will be organized for every different location (Siracusa, Lipari; Himera) and for every different methodological approach (RTI, MICROSCOPE, ARCHAEOLOGY, SNA, EXPERIMENTAL ARCHAEOLOGY).

Fig. 1 Scheme of the folder's organization

They will be stored in Zenodo (community AGATHOCLES) and they will be described using the basic metadata schema of Zenodo which is detailed enough.

2.2 Making data openly accessible:

Data will be stored but they will be put in restricted access because of rights permissions: photo permissions are issued by various Museums only for research purposes. They can't be disseminated and published openly.

Data can be deposited in Zenodo (community AGATHOCLES) and they can be available only through a password-code provided by the Principal Investigator because of the copyright limitations by various Museums and Italian Soprintendenza (Ministry of Cultural Heritage). For this reason images will be available for consultation only upon non-disclosure agreement.

2.3 Making data interoperable:

Interoperability of data is high. Most of the data collected are readable by open softwares (text, sheets, images, video).

Data will be stored in formats as outlined in section 1.1 to allow the re-use of any data as appropriate.

Standard vocabulary used: _photo = standard image by photographic set; _microscope = detailed image by digital microscope set; _video = by a recording video (for experimental archaeological sessions); _RTI = finished file by Reflectance Transformation Imaging post-production.

Appropriate archaeological ontologies will be explored, if useful for interoperability purposes.

2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses):

Original material not covered by third part rights will be associated to a CC BY license.

3. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

No costs for long term preservation in Zenodo: the amount of file-size will be less then 50 GB per record.

4. DATA SECURITY

A daily backup is automatically performed on the cloud storage service.

All data is subject to local backup and backup provision through the cloud based services maintained at the University of Turin (Google Drive).

There are nor security or sensitive data issues.

5. ETHICAL ASPECTS

An informed consent form is planned for the video recording relating to the experimental archaeological sessions.

6. OTHER

None.

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